

Global Warming 1-2100

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Abstract

This work combines global warming data from various publications and datasets, creating a new dataset covering a very long period - from the year 1 to 2100.

The dataset created in this work separates the actual records for the 1-2024 period from the forecast for the 2020-2100 period.

The work includes separate sets for land+ocean (GW), land only (GWL), and ocean only (GWO).

The online dataset is available on the site nowagreen.com.

Glossary

Amp	amplitude of data around trendline
Ave	Average
BAU	Business as Usual
BL	baseline of surface temperature change (GW), pre-industrial = 1850-1900
CF	Conversion Factor across baselines, °C
CF(pBL)	Conversion Factor to 1850-1900 preindustrial baseline, °C
GW	Global Warming, global surface temperature of land+ocean, °C above the 1850-1900 baseline
GWL	global surface temperature over land only, °C above the 1850-1900 baseline
GWO	global surface temperature over the ocean only, °C above the 1850- 1900 baseline
miniAmp	dataset with reduced amplitude
Paleo	Global Warming dataset based on paleoclimate records in the last 2,000 years [1] [2]
pBL	global warming data above 1850-1900 preindustrial period baseline
Ref	reference
Thermo	thermal measurements for determination of global warming using thermometers and satellites (after 1750)
TL	trendline

Global Warming Baseline and Units

All results of calculations in this work are in °C above the preindustrial 1850-1900 baseline (pBL).

Global Warming Land+Ocean Data Sources for the 1-2024 Period

Table 1 - Data sources for the 1-2024 period land+ocean [9]

	Ref	ID	1-1850	1850-1880	1880-1950	1950-2000	2000-2014	2014-2024	
Paleo	[1] [2]	DB11							
Thermo	[1] [2]	DB12							
NASA	[3] [4]	DB13							
NOAA	[5]	DB14							
LBL	[6] [7]	DB15							
IPCC	[8]	DB16							
Ave	[9]	DB17							

Table 2 - Datasets for the 1-2024 period land+ocean [9]

Name	Paleo	Thermo	NASA	NOAA	Berkley Earth	IPCC	Ave
ID	DB11	DB12	DB13	DB14	DB15	DB16	DB17
Reference	[1] [2]	[1] [2]	[3] [4]	[5]	[6] [7]	[8]	[9] [10]
Units	°C	°C	°C	°C	°C	°C	°C
Records	annual	annual	annual	annual	annual	annual	annual
From	1	1850	1880	1850	1850	1950	1
To	2000	2017	2024	2024	2024	2044	2024
Years	2,000	168	145	175	175	95	2024
Baseline (BL)	1961-1990	1961-1990	1951-1980	1901-2000	1951-1980	1850-1900	1850-1900
BL years	30	30	30	100	30	51	51
Ave in BL	-0.0008	0.0000	-0.0003	0.0002	0.0174	N/A	0.0063
Decimal places	4	4	2	2	3	6	3
CF(pBL)	+0.3794	+0.3536	+0.2807	+0.1704	+0.3062	N/A	N/A

The dataset applied in this work is DB17 which is the average of all other datasets converted to the preindustrial baseline in publications [9] [10].

Chart 1 - All datasets - Global Warming (Land+Ocean) 1-2024, °C above pBL

Global Warming over Land Data Sources for the 1750-2024 Period

Table 3 - GWL (land only) data sources for the 1750-2024 period [9]

	Ref	ID	1750-1850	1850-1880	1880-2024
NASA	[3] [4]	DB21			
NOAA	[5]	DB22			
LBL	[6] [7]	DB23			
LBL miniAmp	[6] [7] [9] [10]	DB24			
Ave	[9] [10]	DB25			

Table 4 - GWL (land only) datasets for the 1750-2024 period [9]

Name	NASA	NOAA	Berkley Earth	miniAmp	Ave
ID	DB21	DB22	DB23	DB24	DB25
Reference	[3] [4]	[5]	[6] [7]	[6] [7] [9] [10]	[9] [10]
Units	°C	°C	°C	°C	°C
Records	annual	annual	annual	annual	annual
From	1880	1850	1750	1750	1750
To	2024	2024	2024	2024	2024
Years	145	175	275	275	275
Baseline (BL)	1951-1980	1901-2000	1951-1980	1850-1900	1850-1900
BL years	30	100	30	51	51
Ave in BL	0.0003	0.0000	0.0000	-0.0366	-0.0218
Decimal places	2	2	3	3	3
CF(pBL)	0.4428	+0.4512	+0.4540	N/A	N/A

The dataset applied in this work is DB25 which is the average of DB21, DB22 and DB24 converted to the preindustrial baseline in publications [9] [10].

Chart 2 - GWL (land only) all datasets 1750-2024, °C above pBL

There is very small difference between the datasets, which cannot be distinguished on the above chart (except the 1850-1860 period)

Global Warming over Ocean Data Sources for the 1750-2024 Period

Table 5 - GWO (ocean only) data sources for the 1750-2024 period [9]

	Ref	ID	1750-1850	1850-1880	1880-2024
NASA	[3] [4]	DB31			
NOAA	[5]	DB32			
DB33	DB1+DB25	DB33			
Ave	[9] [10]	DB34			

Table 6 - GWO (ocean only) datasets for the 1750-2024 period [9]

Name	NASA	NOAA	DB33	Ave
ID	DB31	DB32	DB33	DB34
Reference	[3] [4]	[5]	[9]	[9]
Units	°C	°C	°C	°C
Records	annual	annual	annual	annual
From	1880	1850	1750	1750
To	2024	2024	1850	2024
Years	145	175	101	275
Baseline (BL)	1951-1980	1901-2000	1850-1900	1850-1900
BL years	30	100	51	51
Ave in BL	0.0007	0.0000	N/A	0.0025
Decimal places	2	2	3	3
CF(pBL)	+0.0981	+0.0441	N/A	N/A

The dataset applied in this work is DB34 which is the average of all other datasets converted to the preindustrial baseline in publications [9] [10].

Chart 3 - GWO (ocean only) all datasets 1750-2024, °C above pBL

There is very small difference between the datasets, which cannot be distinguished on the above chart.

Global Warming Land+Ocean Forecast

The forecast is based on four methods as described in publication [11].

All methods are for the business as usual CO₂ mitigation scenario.

The methods are [11]:

- parabolic trendline of the last 61 years of global warming (GWTL)
- velocity and acceleration of global warming (GWA)
- parabolic trendline of the last 61 years of cumulated CO₂ emissions (CO₂TL)
- velocity and acceleration cumulative CO₂ emissions (CO₂A)

The average result from all four methods for the business as usual CO₂ mitigation scenario in 2100 is 4.4°C (4.1°C -5.0°C).

Chart 4 - Business as usual (BAU) GW forecast using all methods, °C above 1850-1900 baseline, for land+ocean [11]

The dataset applied in this work is Ave which is the average of all other datasets considered in publications [11].

Global Warming over Land (GWL) and Global Warming over Ocean (GWO) Forecast

The forecast is based on the optimal trendline as selected in publication [12].
All trendlines are for the business as usual CO₂ mitigation scenario.

Table 7 - Selected option [12]

ID	Option 4-1
Parameter	GWO/GW
Trendline	Power
from	1940
to	2021
k	0.992427705218
p	-0.046868903112
R2	0.0576
GWL in 2030, °C	2.15
GWO in 2030, °C	1.20
GWL in 2100, °C	6.52
GWO in 2100, °C	3.45

Chart 5 - BAU forecast 2020-2100 using the selected trendline: Option 4-1: GWO/GW 1940-2021 Power Trendline, °C above pBL [12] [13]

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Chart 6 - Global Warming 1-2100 °C above pBL

The dataset according to this work is publically available in publication [14] and online on site nowagreen.com

References

1. IPCC - Changes in global surface temperature reconstructed from paleoclimate archives (1-2000)
2. Kaufman, D., McKay, N., Routson, C. et al. Holocene global mean surface temperature, a multi-method reconstruction approach. *Sci Data* 7, 201 (2020)
3. GISS Surface Temperature Analysis (GISTEMP), NASA Goddard Institute for Space Studies
<https://data.giss.nasa.gov/gistemp>
4. Lenssen, N., G. Schmidt, J. Hansen, M. Menne, A. Persin, R. Ruedy, and D. Zyss, 2019: Improvements in the GISTEMP uncertainty model. *J. Geophys. Res. Atmos.*, 124, no. 12, 6307-6326, doi:10.1029/2018JD029522
5. NOAA National Centers for Environmental Information - Climate at a Glance
<https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/monitoring/climate-at-a-glance>
6. Berkeley Earth - Global Warming - Global Temperature Data
<https://berkeleyearth.org/data/>
7. Rohde, R. A. and Hausfather, Z.: The Berkeley Earth Land/Ocean Temperature Record, *Earth Syst. Sci. Data*, 12, 3469-3479, 2020,
<https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-12-3469-2020>
8. IPCC Sixth Assessment Report, Working Group I
<https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/>

9. Global Warming Datasets 1-2024 - Joseph Nowarski,
DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15013054
10. Global Warming Dataset Land+Ocean (1-2024), Land only (1750-2024),
Ocean only (1750-2024) – Joseph Nowarski, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15013056
11. Global Warming Forecast Using Acceleration Factors - Joseph Nowarski,
DOI:10.5281/zenodo.6621042
12. Global Warming Forecast over the Land and over the Ocean - Joseph
Nowarski, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.14581167
13. Dataset Global Warming Forecast over the Land and over the Ocean -
Joseph Nowarski, DOI:10.5281/zenodo.14581169
14. Dataset Global Warming 1-2100 - Joseph Nowarski,
DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15034765

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